

THE STUDY OF THE PROBLEM OF ADOLESCENT MENTAL DEVELOPMENT AND ABILITIES IN MODERN PSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract. *The article explores the notions of "adaptation" and "socialization" in adolescents, evaluates the indicators of effective adaptation, and highlights instances of adolescent maladaptation.*

Keywords: *adaptation, teenager, socialization, maladaptation, successful adaptation.*

INTRODUCTION

The radical social, political and economic changes taking place in the country and the world affect and complicate the conditions of social life of each person, change the socio-cultural situation that influences the formation and development of the individual. The criteria of mental and psychological health and safety are now put first both in public policy and in the education system, since along with the decline in the birth rate, the quality of physical, mental and psychological health of children is deteriorating, the level of social maladjustment and various types of deviant behavior of children and adolescents is increasing. The standard of living is closely related to the quality of life, and the quality of life in world analogues is the optimal implementation of the psychophysiological, socio-public gifts of each individual [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Traditionally, adaptation is understood as the process of a person entering a new environment and adjusting to the conditions. This is a universal phenomenon of all living things, which can be observed both in the plant and animal worlds. Adaptation - from the Latin "I adapt" - is a complex process of adjustment of the organism, which occurs at different levels: physiological, social, psychological. Adaptation of the organism to new conditions of social existence, to a new regime is accompanied by changes in the child's behavior, sleep disorders, appetite. Adaptation is an active process that leads either to positive (adaptability, that is, the totality of all useful changes in the body and psyche) results, or negative consequences (stress). In this case, two main criteria for successful adaptation are distinguished: internal comfort (emotional satisfaction) and external adequacy of behavior (the ability to easily and accurately fulfill new requirements). When a child enters a nursery, a new stage in his or her life begins.

Social adaptation is the process of mastering a system of knowledge, norms, values, attitudes, and behavior patterns cultivated by a particular society, social community, or group.

The adaptation situation is associated with the relative isolation of the child: the emphasis is on the biological component of adaptation, the process of adjusting to the influence of various environmental factors. The child masters culture through the mediation of an adult. A social adult interprets general cultural values in the context of the child's individual characteristics. Human nature is genetically endowed with a great capacity for adaptation. Practice and scientific research show that a person has significant adaptive abilities in the conditions of the natural and social environment, changing even within critical limits.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The range of social roles that are tried on expands. Psychological difficulties of growing up, contradictory and unstable self-images appear. That is why communication of teenagers with peers and adults should be considered the most important psychological condition of their personal development. Failures in communication lead to internal discomfort, which cannot be compensated for by any objectively high indicators in other spheres of life and activity. Communication is subjectively perceived by teenagers as something very important personally: this is evidenced by their sensitive attention to the form of communication, its tonality, trust, attempts to comprehend and analyze their relationships with peers and adults. If a child at school cannot find a system of communication that satisfies him, he “leaves” school, more often psychologically, although not so rarely literally. This is a manifestation of socio-psychological maladjustment, the signs of which are considered to be increased anxiety and lack of self-confidence, aggressiveness and a feeling of inferiority, excessive passion for smoking, computers, long-term intrapersonal and interpersonal conflicts experienced without searching for possible solutions [2]. It is traditionally believed that socialization was successful if a student has learned the norms, values and rules of behavior accepted in society and school. One can agree with this approach, but only when the situation in society is sufficiently stable. Our society is in a state of "social disorganization" - this means that cultural values, norms and expectations contradict each other. There are groups of people who have different attitudes to the same social phenomena, and accordingly, different norms and ideas operate in their environment.

In such conditions it is quite difficult to determine the success or failure of socialization. It is impossible to answer the question of the success of socialization unequivocally on the basis of existing criteria. It is believed that the success of socialization is determined by three factors: social expectations, behavioral change, and the desire for conformity (an individual's agreement with the goals of society and the use of legal means). Human life takes place within various social groups of which an individual is a member. It is the group of which a particular person is a member that is the source of the values that are formed in him, the world of his communication. However, an individual appropriates group norms as his own only when this group is a “reference group for him – a real or ideal group to which a person is oriented, whose values, ideals, and norms he shares.” The antipode of a reference group is a membership group – a person can be a member of this group, but internally remain indifferent to its goals and norms. In this case, he remains a member of this group and complies with the norms accepted in it due to the threat of losing this group or his place in it, or due to fear of social sanctions. This phenomenon is called conformism; it is now considered one of the main mechanisms for maintaining the integrity of the group, the unity of its values and goals. As a member of any group, an individual is successfully socialized when his behavior corresponds to group expectations, when he changes his behavior in accordance with these expectations, when his behavior is conformal, that is, he obeys the norms accepted in the group. A normally proceeding process of socialization implies the internalization of social norms and values by the individual. This is unlikely to happen if the individual does not share the norms and values accepted in the group and adheres to them only under group pressure or out of fear of punishment. Consequently, the process of socialization of a teenager proceeds successfully only when he finds a reference group: the school team, class and external norms of this group pass into the internal plan of regulation of the teenager's behavior. It is known from developmental psychology that each age corresponds to its own reference group, which is the main institution of socialization during this period. Thus, the success of socialization of a teenager depends on the

functioning of the social institution of the school, which is mainly responsible for his socialization at this age stage [3].

It is possible to identify the signs or criteria of successful socialization.

Firstly, a schoolchild must be in a reference group, since its norms and values play a decisive role in his socialization, in his assimilation of a certain social experience and the formation of internal behavioral regulators, the internal plane of consciousness.

Secondly, conditions for successful group activity must be created in the group. These conditions will be favorable in the following cases [6]:

a) the schoolchild has the opportunity to realize and express himself in the general group activity;

b) his activity is approved by the group members;

c) the schoolchild has a high status and recognition in the group.

Thirdly, the success of socialization can be judged on the basis of such subjective criteria as the teenager's satisfaction with the environment in which he finds himself; successful mastery of the leading activity; the teenager's ability to establish long-term interpersonal contacts with different people; an age-appropriate idea of the teenager about himself, his abilities, the ability to evaluate the results of his activities.

Fourthly, the successful process of socialization is evidenced by the fact that the teenager is not rejected from the social institutions with which he needs to interact (family, school, extracurricular institutions).

Another criterion for the success of socialization can be called the approval of the teenager as successful in his life not only by the members of the group in which he is, but also by other people around him (neighbors, teachers, peers, and so on) [5].

The success of socialization is also determined by the extent to which the teenager has satisfied his needs; how wide the choice of behavioral options aimed at satisfying needs is; how favorable are the living conditions for satisfying needs. The socialization of a teenager, his acquisition of social experience, occurs as he becomes more and more actively involved in multifaceted and diverse public-school relations, as his diverse connections with the surrounding world expand. When a teenager has mastered various methods of interaction with the school environment, which allows him to successfully satisfy his needs without causing harm to himself and others, then we can confidently say that he has successfully socialized [4].

CONCLUSION

At present, the goal of school education is not to create ideal conditions for a child, implying a knowledge-rich environment, but to ensure that the younger generation is well-rounded in their entry into adulthood. One of these aspects is the variety of competencies that are based on the educational environment. First of all, these are the ability to analyze and synthesize, the ability to organize and plan, basic general knowledge and general knowledge of professions, communication skills in the native language, basic computer skills, information management skills (the ability to extract and analyze information from various sources), the ability to solve problems and make decisions. Knowledge about students is necessary for the successful implementation of the competency-based approach. Therefore, within the framework of the diagnostic direction of activity carried out by a psychologist, it is possible to obtain comprehensive information about the current knowledge, skills and abilities of a schoolchild, his motives and values, in other words, about his existing competencies and the level of their formation. This information will allow to

build an optimal trajectory of professionalization of a future student in order to acquire new and improve existing competencies necessary for the chosen profession.

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